

Supplemental information

Unraveling Nanoarchitectonics-Driven Metal-Support Interactions and Size Effects Governing CO Oxidation Activity of Size-Selected Pt Clusters on TiO₂ and SnO₂ Supports

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Figure S1. Mass spectra of the molecular beam of pure Pt_n⁺ clusters with the Cluster Deposition Instrument optimized for the production of Pt₁₃ (top) and Pt₄₀ (bottom) clusters, recorded at lowered resolution to provide the highest flux of deposited clusters.

Figure S2. AFM height images ($0.5 \mu\text{m} \times 0.5 \mu\text{m}$) measured in tapping mode for: (a) blank Si substrate with the native oxide layer; (b) 1.5 nm TiO_2 layer on SiO_2/Si substrate; and (c) 1.5 nm SnO_2 layer on SiO_2/Si substrate. The mean roughness R_a was 0.1 nm, 0.1 nm, and 0.2 nm for SiO_2 , TiO_2 , and SnO_2 , respectively.

Figure S3. Evolution of the high-resolution NAP-XPS Ti 2p spectra with temperature ramping from RT to 350 °C, acquired *in-situ* during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) $\text{Pt}_{13}/\text{TiO}_2$ and (b) $\text{Pt}_{40}/\text{TiO}_2$. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at the pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5 % CO and 2.5 % O_2 at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity.

Figure S4. Evolution of the high-resolution NAP-XPS Sn 3d spectra with temperature ramping from RT to 350 °C, acquired *in-situ* during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) Pt₁₃/SnO₂ and (b) Pt₄₀/SnO₂. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at the pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5 % CO and 2.5 % O₂ at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity.

Figure S5. Evolution of the high-resolution NAP-XPS C 1s spectra with temperature ramping from RT to 350 °C, acquired *in-situ* during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) Pt₁₃/TiO₂ and (b) Pt₁₃/SnO₂. All spectra were normalized to the maximum intensity of C 1s peak obtained at RT to show how carbon content decreases with temperature. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at the pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5 % CO and 2.5 % O₂ at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar.

Table S1. XPS chemical composition obtained before (b) and after (c) sputtering for 3 different Pt₄₀/SnO₂ catalysts: 1 – after catalytic test at TPR, 2 – after NAP-XPS measurements, and 3 – pristine (as-deposited).

Pt₄₀/SnO₂ samples:		C 1s, at.%	N 1s, at.%	O 1s, at.%	Pt 4f, at.%	Si 2p, at.%	Sn 3d, at.%
after TPR	unspattered	23.5	2.0	32.3	1.4	31.6	9.1
	sputtered	6.0	0.6	34.2	1.7	44.8	12.7
after NAP-XPS	unspattered	28.6	1.8	31.5	1.0	29.2	7.8
	sputtered	6.3	0.9	33.5	1.4	46.0	11.9
as-deposited	unspattered	42.1	3.6	25.9	1.1	21.9	5.4
	sputtered	7.6	1.1	25.4	1.2	54.6	10.1
Blank SnO₂	unspattered	24.8	1.2	32.3	0.0	29.1	12.6
	sputtered	10.4	0.8	30.9	0.0	40.6	17.3